

THE PHASE-DIAGRAM STUDIES OF THE BINARY SYSTEMS. PART II.
SALOL-DIPHENYL, SALOL-ACENAPHTHENE AND
SALOL-PHENANTHRENE

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The studies of the phase-diagrams of the binary systems of salol with diphenyl, acenaphthene and phenanthrene have disclosed formation of simple eutectics of all the three systems and there is no existence of any chemical union between them. Application of the Clapeyron equation reveals very slight departure from ideal solutions.

In a previous communication of the series (Majumdar and Rakshit, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 157) the studies of the phase-diagram of salol-naphthalene have been reported. The present investigation deals with freezing point-composition curves of the binary systems of salol with three other hydrocarbons, viz., diphenyl, acenaphthene and phenanthrene, from their thermal analysis. Each of these mixtures of salol and hydrocarbons readily begins to liquefy even at ordinary temperature and it would be of interest to investigate if any chemical change is involved therein.

Literature records very few such studies with salol, and these have been referred to in the previous communication. With the hydrocarbons, mentioned above, there are several binary systems which have been studied (Lee and Warner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 318; Klochko-Zhovnir, *J. Appl. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1949, 22, 848) and eutectic systems have been shown to exist with the exception of the systems acenaphthene and some nitro compounds (Efremov *et al.*, *Bull. Acad. Sci., U.S.S.R.*, 1936, 515; *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 59, 373).

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used were chemical reagent varieties of B.D.H. The purity was checked always by freezing point determination by means of cooling curves. The data corresponded with the internationally accepted values. A point should, however, be noted regarding phenanthrene. The sample of phenanthrene used was recrystallised several times, and the constant m.p. was 99.2°. But the solution of phenanthrene in alcohol exhibited some fluorescence in actinic rays, which might be due to contamination with traces of anthracene. Further purification was not possible. Solid solution of anthracene in phenanthrene was known and the sample of phenanthrene of maximum purity obtained by Cohen and Cormier (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930; 52, 4363) had the m.p. 99-99.5°. Phenanthrene obtained by us was therefore taken as the purest available.

The experimental procedure was the same as followed in our previous studies (*loc. cit.*) Only in some of our experiments, particularly with phenanthrene, the cooling was effected slowly in a paraffin bath of somewhat lower temperature, instead of the air-jacket of the Dewar flask. The usual corrections for supercooling and exposed stem of the thermometer were made.

Salol-diphenyl.—The data of freezing points for various compositions are recorded in Table I and the corresponding plot in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point.		Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point.		Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point.	
	Initial.	Final.		Initial.	Final.		Initial.	Final.
100	42.0°	42.0°	71	...	23.38°	40	49.56°	
97	33.62°	...	70	24.98°	23.40°	30	55.43°	
80	27.19°	23.38°	66	28.00°	...	20	60.50°	
73	23.38°	23.38°	65	33.52°	23.38°	10	64.97°	
72	...	23.38°	50	42.79°	...	0	68.94°	68.94°

In the temperature-composition graph there is one single point which is a minimum and where the liquidus from either side meet the solidus. The system therefore admits of no chemical union but behaves as a simple eutectic. The eutectic point is 23.38° and the corresponding composition is 73% salol and 27% diphenyl by weight. The eutectic point has been confirmed by taking a mixture of the above-mentioned composi-

FIG. 1.

tion which melts and freezes at the same temperature as noted above. It has also been corroborated by the fact that the second arrest point in time-temperature (cooling) curves also corresponds to the same temperature 23.38°. This latter fact shows further that the two components would not form a solid solution. Besides, the crystals separating in the initial stages of cooling above the eutectic temperature, on the right and left sides of the eutectic point, were pure salol and diphenyl respectively, verified from their

melting points. The solidified mixtures of different compositions also begin to melt at the same temperature, clearly proving the eutectic nature. A cooling curve is shown in Fig. 2 to show the nature of the arrest points.

FIG. 2

Salol-acenaphthene.—The mixture, having the eutectic composition of 84.1% salol and 15.9% acenaphthene by weight, indicated by the intersection of the liquidus curves, freezes at 30.37°. The freezing temperatures for various compositions are shown in Table II and the corresponding plot in Fig. 1.

TABLE II

Salol-acenaphthene.

Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point. Initial.	Final.	Wt. % of salol	Freezing point. Initial.	Final.	Wt. % of Initial.	Freezing point. salol.	Final.
100	42.00°	42.0°	78.7	33.42°	30.2°	40.0	74.59°	
94.0	36.96°	30.37°	75.5	13.68°		30.0	80.07°	
84.1	30.37°	30.37°	70.0	49.44°		20.0	84.20°	
80.0	...	30.0°	60.0	60.43°		10.0	88.50°	
						0	94.70°	94.7°

That there is no appreciable solubility of the components in the solid state has been proved by isolating the primary crystals of acenaphthene and salol. The constancy of the second arrest point for almost all the mixtures studied also excludes the possibility of any appreciable solid solution.

Salol-phenanthrene.—This system has a eutectic composition of 78.06% salol and 21.94% phenanthrene by weight, and a freezing temperature 28.26°. The freezing points for various mixtures are recorded in Table III and the corresponding plot in Fig. 1

TABLE III

Salol-phenanthrene.

Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point.		Wt.% of salol.	Freezing point		Wt. % of salol.	Freezing point	
	Initial.	Final.		Initial.	Final.		Initial.	Final
100.00	42.0°	42.0°	80.21	28.27°	28.27°	60.74	51.10°	
96.55	39.2°	...	78.06	28.26°	28.26°	48.78	63.19°	
91.26	36.28°	26.97°	71.82	35.60°	27.22°	40.57	71.10°	
85.75	32.87°	28.22°	64.50	45.12°	27.9°	26.91	81.55°	
						0	99.2°	99.2°

Phenanthrene-salol system belongs to the simple eutectic type; the absence of solid solution has been confirmed in a manner similar to that followed in other two systems. The ideal solubilities have been calculated, after taking into consideration, the variation of ΔH_f with temperature, from the following equations (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 318):

$$\log N (\text{naphthalene}) = (518.9/T) + 19.170 \log T - 0.0115 T - 46.253$$

$$\log N (\text{diphenyl}) = -(274.0/T) + 4.380 \log T - 10.299$$

$$\log N (\text{phenanthrene}) = -(945.2/T) + 2.540$$

In the case of phenanthrene, however, $\Delta H_f = 4325$ cal./mole (Hodgman, "Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics") for the hydrocarbon at its m.p. has been used. The ideal solubilities and eutectic temperatures are shown in Table IV (see also Majumdar and Rakshit, *loc. cit.*). In calculating eutectic temperatures, use has been made of the equation,

$$\log N = - \frac{\Delta H_f}{2.303R} [(1/T) - (1/T^0)],$$

where N stands for the mole fraction of salol at eutectic composition and ΔH_f , its molar latent heat of fusion at its melting point. This calculation is approximate to the extent that variation of ΔH_f for salol with temperature is not known and has not been taken into account.

TABLE IV

Systems.	Eutectic composition.		Eutectic temperature.	
	Mole. fraction (salol).			
	Expt.	*Ideal.	Expt.	Calc. from ΔH_f of salol.
Salol-naphthalene	0.7158	0.6888	25.49°	21.5°
Salol-diphenyl	0.6606	0.6050	23.38°	20.2°
Salol-acenaphthene	0.7920	...	30.37°	29.1°
Salol-phenanthrene	0.7476	0.7471	28.26°	26.1°

*Calc. from ΔH_f of hydrocarbons.

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